

Easy creation of reproducible computational workflows with SciWIn-Client

Jens Krumsieck¹ <https://orcid.org/00009-0007-1765-0527>,
Patrick König² <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4800-2833>

¹ Thünen Institute, Braunschweig, Germany

² Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetic and Crop Plant Research (IPK), Gatersleben, Germany

Abstract

Computational workflows are used in many different disciplines to automate complex, multi-step data analysis procedures. To ensure reproducibility, scalability and efficiency in scientific research, lots of effort has been put into domain specific languages that formalize and standardize computational scientific work. The *Common Workflow Language* (CWL)^[1] is among the most powerful and established workflow languages. While CWL is an extremely flexible language, is also quite verbose. To facilitate the creation of CWL files, *SciWIn-Client*, which is written in the Rust programming language, offers a simple command line interface. SciWIn-Client is the first building block of the **Scientific Workflow Infrastructure** which is a key part of the FAIRagro consortium's service portfolio.

CWL workflows are structured as directed acyclic graphs where individual steps are connected through their inputs and outputs. A CWL *CommandLineTool* represents a single executable step in a workflow. A CWL *Workflow* acts as a container for multiple steps, connects multiple tools and manages dependencies between steps.

SciWIn-Client creates CWL *CommandLineTools* by capturing and analyzing the CLI command-line used by the researcher in their usual routine to carry out computational tasks. Steps represented by CWL *CommandLineTools* can be connected into complex workflows by using simple commands to build the directed acyclic graph edge by edge. Designed as an unobtrusive lean CLI program, SciWIn-Client integrates seamlessly into the researcher's toolbox providing for provenance management what Git delivers for version control.

SciWIn-Client thus helps to implement FAIR data- and code handling practices right at the digital workbench. Next to the reproducibility and traceability of computational processes, scientists gain the ability package their intermediate and final results into FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs). We develop multiple export options, including *Workflow RO-Crates*^[2] that can be published on *workflowhub.eu*, *ARCs*^[3] that are compatible with DataPLANT's *PLANTdataHUB*^[3], and *Provenance Run Crate*^[4] as the most advanced FDO type. Furthermore, the CWL workflows created by SciWIn-Client can be executed by remote execution engines such as Reana^[5] and thus provide easy access to high performance compute infrastructure.

Resources

SciWIn Client Repository: https://github.com/fairagro/m4.4_sciwin_client

Funding

This work was created as part of the NFDI consortium FAIRagro (www.fairagro.net). We gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the German Research Foundation (DFG) – project number 501899475.

References

- [1] M. R. Crusoe et al., “Methods Included: Standardizing Computational Reuse and Portability with the Common Workflow Language,” *Commun. ACM*, vol. 65, no. 6, pp. 54–63, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1145/3486897.
- [2] Bacall F, Williams AR, Owen S, Soiland-Reyes S. Workflow RO-Crate Profile 1.0. WorkflowHub community, 2022. <https://w3id.org/workflowhub/workflow-ro-crate/1.0>.
- [3] a) H. L. Weil et al., “PLANTdataHUB: a collaborative platform for continuous FAIR data sharing in plant research,” *Plant J.*, vol. 116, no. 4, pp. 974–988, 2023, doi: 10.1111/tpj.16474. b) C. Garth, “Immutable yet evolving: ARCs for permanent sharing in the research data-time continuum,” in *E-Science-Tage 2021: Share Your Research Data*, V. Heuveline et al., Eds. Heidelberg: heiBOOKS, 2022, pp. 366–373, doi: 10.11588/heibooks.979.c13751
- [4] S. Leo et al., “Recording provenance of workflow runs with RO-Crate,” *PLOS ONE*, vol. 19, no. 9, p. e0309210, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0309210.
- [5] T. Šimko, L. Heinrich, H. Hirvonsalo, D. Kousidis, and D. Rodríguez, “REANA: A System for Reusable Research Data Analyses,” *EPJ Web Conf.*, vol. 214, p. 06034, 2019, doi: 10.1051/epjconf/201921406034.